

Neo Forge Lab - Community Introduction Guide

Welcome to the **Neo Forge Lab** community on Zenodo. This document serves as an introductory guide to understanding our mission, areas of focus, and how to participate in this innovative research and development initiative.

1. About Neo Forge Lab

Neo Forge Lab is a research and development division of CYBERSAFENET NORMAS E COMPLIANCE, dedicated to fostering innovation and improving global connections through advanced technological solutions. Our mission is to push the boundaries of science, technology, and ethics to address global challenges. We aim to create a collaborative ecosystem that bridges academia, industry, and society.

2. Roadmap of Focus Areas

The Neo Forge Lab explores the following key domains:

- **Internet of Things (IoT):** Developing interconnected solutions for optimizing processes across industries.
- **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** Innovating data-driven systems for real-time decision-making and automation.
- **Cybersecurity:** Advancing tools and protocols to safeguard digital assets and networks.
- **Mesh Networks and Connectivity:** Expanding access to reliable communication in underserved areas.
- **Digital Healthcare (Healthcare):** Creating technologies to enhance health monitoring, diagnostics, and care delivery.
- **Global Finance and Banking Systems:** Designing secure solutions for efficient international financial transactions.
- **Smart City Infrastructure:** Developing sustainable urban technologies for smarter living.
- **Governance, Ethics, and Sustainability in IT:** Establishing frameworks for ethical and sustainable use of technology.

3. Community Mission

Our Zenodo community aims to:

- Foster global collaboration in groundbreaking research.
- Share open-access resources, findings, and tools.
- Engage researchers, students, and organizations in joint projects.
- Support the dissemination of innovative ideas and technologies.

4. How to Participate

We invite researchers, industry professionals, students, and enthusiasts to:

1. **Contribute Research:** Submit your work aligned with our roadmap areas.
2. **Collaborate:** Join ongoing projects or propose new initiatives.
3. **Engage:** Follow and support the community through discussions and shared resources.

5. Curation Policy

The Neo Forge Lab community ensures that all submissions:

- Align with our focus areas.
- Maintain high-quality standards in methodology and presentation.
- Promote open-access and knowledge-sharing principles.

Our curators review submissions to ensure compliance with these guidelines, fostering a valuable resource hub for all members.

6. Useful Links

- **Website:** [Neo Forge Lab](#)
- **LinkedIn:** [Neo Forge Lab Community](#)
- **Zenodo Community Page:** [Neo Forge Lab on Zenodo](#)

7. Contact Information

For inquiries or collaboration proposals, reach out to us via:

- **Email:** cybersafenetnc@gmail.com

Thank you for joining us in shaping a better, connected world through innovation and collaboration.